

This badge was issued
Expires on March 31, 2024

Verification

- ✓ Issued on March 31, 2024
- ✓ Issued by Amazon Web Services Training and Certification
- ✓ Issued using Credly
- ✓ Issued to Manohar Karanth P D
- ✓ Accepted on April 01, 2024
- ✓ Last Updated April 01, 2024
- ✓ **VERIFIED**

✓ Verified

🎉 Celebrate

Associate

how to use AWS services to
optimize cost and performance
technical expertise to understand
they are familiar with
na design, and optimal data store